

DESCRIPTION OF THE FEMALE CHARACTER IN HAMLET AND MACBETH.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854616>

Annatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Shekisperming tragediyalarida ayollar sahnadagi roli haqidagi izlanishlarni o'rganish, uning ayollar va ularning jamiyatdagi o'рни haqidagi his tuyg'ularni ko'rsatish uchun umumiy tushuncha berishga harakat qildim. Shuningdek Shekspirning asosiy fojialari Gamlet va Makbet asosiy manba sifatida olingan. Bizga malumki dast avval tetrlar paydo bo'lgandan beri ayollar rolini har doim sahnada erkaklar, odatda yosh bolalar o'ynagan. Shekspir yaratgan ayollari har bir davrga moslashgan, ular ayollar haqidagi o'zgaruvchan g'oyalar bilan bog'liq holda shakllangan va qayta jobizalantirgan. Shekspir o'z asarlarida, sahnada va sahifada yashagan va nafas olgan ayollarni yaratdi. Ular zukkolik, shuhratpastlik va muhabbat kabi buyuk qadryatlar va fazilatlarini ifodalagan. Maqolada spektakllarda qanday ayollar tasvirlangani, ayol qahramonlarning xatti-harakatlari qanday qoidalar bilan tartibga solingani va ayol obrazlari jamiyatga qarshi fitna uyushtirish haqidagi bazi fikrlarni beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ofeliya, Gertruda, Makbet xonim, davr, itoatkorlik, ziddiyatlar, zaif va xavfli.

Аннотация: В этой статье я постарался дать общее представление об исследованиях роли женщин на сцене в трагедиях Шекспира, показать его чувства к женщинам и их месту в обществе. В качестве первоисточников также взяты главные трагедии Шекспира «Гамлет» и «Макбет». Мы знаем, что с момента возникновения тетр женские роли всегда играли мужчины, обычно маленькие дети. Женщины, созданные Шекспиром, адаптировались к каждой эпохе, они формировались и видоизменялись в связи с меняющимися представлениями о женщине. Шекспир создал женщин, которые жили и дышали в его произведениях, на сцене и на страницах. Они олицетворяли великие ценности и добродетели, такие как интеллект, честолюбие и любовь. В статье даются некоторые представления о том, как изображаются женщины в пьесах, какие правила регулируют поведение женских персонажей и как женские персонажи устраивают заговоры против общества.

Ключевые слова: Офелия, Гертруда, период леди Макбет, послушание, конфликты, слабые и опасные.

Abstract: In this article, I tried to give a general understanding of research on the role of women on the stage in the tragedies of Shakspear, to show his feelings about women and their place in society. Shakespeare's major tragedies Hamlet and Macbeth are also taken as primary sources. We know that since the beginning of tetras, the roles of women have always been played by men, usually young children. The women created by Shakespeare adapted to each era, they were formed and reshaped in connection with the changing ideas about women. Shakespeare created women who lived and breathed in his works, on stage and on the page. They represented great values and virtues such as intelligence, ambition and love. The article gives some ideas about how women are portrayed in plays, what rules regulate the behavior of female characters, and how female characters conspire against society.

Key words: Ophelia, Gertrude, Lady Macbeth period, obedience, conflicts, weak and dangerous.

The literary heritage of William Shakespeare, one of the great figures of world literature, is made up of high art examples that embody ancient and literary universal values.

Historical data shows that by studying Shakespeare's global reputation, we can learn about his place and position in today's literary world. His centuries were accepted in the four corners of the world and adapted to their modern theater and cinema. At that time, the position of women in society was extremely deplorable. If we look at the era in which Shakespeare lived, it depended on the rules of the Elizabethan era. The era demanded that women could be seen but not heard.

Therefore, it was customary for women to marry in exchange for power, inheritance, dowry and land. Single women were the property of their fathers or husbands. Although Elizabeth I was not married, the role of women in society was very limited. During the time of the Queen, women were considered weak and vulnerable. In addition, women had to express virtues such as obedience, chastity, silence, and piety. All these qualities naturally have their meaning in relationships. The distribution of roles in Elizabethan society was strictly regulated; men were to eat bread and women were to be submissive. Nevertheless, within this deprived, stable and established framework, the images of women are depicted in different ways in Shakespeare's plays, in which

she represents a very conflicted female figure of the Renaissance. In Shakespeare's works, it took place in very complex and difficult conditions, in the process of sharp changes between the new and the old. Through Shakespeare's works, women appeared as supporting and central characters. The roles of Hamlet, Ophelia and Gertrude in particular, may represent foreshadowing. It should be noted that both female characters are of great importance to the development of the play. Because these two guide Hamlet's thinking in opposition to the idea of love. Ophelia represents the role of a submissive, sober, innocent but corrupt woman in this play. Many of the men in the play, such as his King Claudius and even his father Polonius, use their supreme power as king to manipulate Hamlet to their advantage. But in the century, it can be seen that Ophelia is afraid to be in contact with Hamlet and leaves him. Gertrude is a woman with a very strong personality. Two months after her ex-husband's death, she marries her husband's brother and rules the kingdom in the same position as the king to show how important power is. However, he wants to keep the crown. Hamlet seems to be the only character who notices this. Gertrude's guilt as a mother figure affects Hamlet's thoughts about women, even Ophelia. All this changes Hamlet's perception of love and trust.

Between 1599 and 1606, William Shakespeare wrote the tragedy Macbeth, shortened to Macbeth during the Jacobean period. The play is set in Scotland and explores how politics, combined with destructive psychological influences, can't work if one wants to gain power. Macbeth is a Scottish general, the main character of the play. At the beginning of the play, when the audience is introduced to Macbeth as a male figure who has fought in many wars, Lady Macbeth enters the scene. Immediately the image of an ideal person melts away. Macbeth and Lady Macbeth have a relationship that goes against the traditions of early modern England and challenges the ideal of gender structure in society. The general marries the power-hungry Lady Macbeth and convinces her husband to kill the king to make himself king. This terrible bloodshed leads Macbeth and Lady Macbeth to a battle of madness and ultimately death. In the play, Lady Macbeth shows her contempt for Macbeth's "bad weakness" because after receiving Macbeth's letter containing details of the "Strange Sisters" prophecy, Lady Macbeth immediately questions her husband's character. At this point, it is clear that Lady Macbeth thinks that her husband, although he has some ambition, lacks a lot of courage. He is afraid of her nature, and says that she is filled with so much milk that it makes her without "sickness" or the drive

that compels her to act, and thus be able to protect the crown. Lady Macbeth seems to be convinced that she must give up her femininity in order to achieve her dashing courage and thus be successful.

A ghost appears in Hamlet and persuades him to seek revenge, but in Macbeth's case, Lady Macbeth should be the one who persuades Macbeth to act. He orders: "Hie thee hither, that I may pour my spirits in thine ear."

Ruth Leila Anderson, author of Elizabethan psychology and Shakespeare's plays, explains that during the summer season, "spirits flee from the body with the exhalation ... Cholera is on the rise."

Shakespeare made many references to the physiological and psychological beliefs of Renaissance and early modern English society in his plays. Although his plays are not set in England, they still reflect modern ideology. Shakespeare exposes the ambiguities and ideological aspects of his texts subversively, engages in a different form of politics and, more specifically, addresses the problems of his own context. World literature has shown a number of talented artists over the years, whose spiritual legacy has been shaking the hearts of readers for centuries.

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